

Research Diary

CoAct for Mental Health

This booklet wants to accompany you as a co-researcher in the research of citizen science of CoActuem per la Salut Mental. It will help you to reflect on support networks in mental health through your own experience, which is what drives this project.

We hope you enjoy this search and thank you so much for your trust!

This notebook belongs to:

Name of the people in your group:

Group:

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Share experiences

Precisely because we are all different people, your personal experience will also resonate differently with the people who will read from you in the chatbot.

Your stories will serve to weave an extensive network of shared experiences. For this reason, you should value experiences related to social support networks. What experiences have been lived by the same people? How close are they to these experiences? Has the one who read it in the chatbot lived it? Has anyone in your closest circle experienced it?

Here is an example to guide you with the format that will appear in the chatbot (maximum length of 300 characters):

“During confinement, I have often been overwhelmed by having to deal with not only my own fears and anxieties, but also those of my children. I shared it with moms and parents around me and many were in the same situation. They didn't know what to do either.”

Now it's your turn! In the following, we ask you to write your own stories in the worksheets we have prepared. We will work on them together in the sessions and, at some point, we will ask you to send it to us at coactuem@ub.edu.

Share experiences

Would you like to accompany the story with a drawing? Tell us how you imagine it or make a sketch.

What is the identifying of your story? (will not be visible in the chatbot)